

Course on GIS and Remote Sensing Data to monitor forest ecosystem

Introduction

To monitor stress and the impacts of climate change on forests, there is a need to enhance the technical analysis skills of individuals involved in sustainable forest management. In recent years, various tools like Sentinel-2 satellite imagery have allowed for almost continuous monitoring of such stress.

However, technological progress has not led to a real change because many technicians do not know how to use analysis tools, even simple ones. In this context, within the GO-SURF project, it was decided to organize a tailored 24-hour course to teach forest management technicians how to use these tools and the related GIS (Geographic Information System) tools for analysis. The course has been highly successful with over 50 participants enrolled. The course was structured with practical exercises conducted in classroom settings tailored to the forestry sector. In particular, the Google Earth Engine analysis platform and data easily implementable into the QGIS system were used. This enabled the transfer of analytical capabilities to the technicians who attended the course, many of whom had no prior knowledge of the potential of these tools.

Lessons learned

The technicians emphasized that courses of this kind are crucial, especially in a forestry context. The strength of the course lay in its practical aspect, with exercises specifically designed to address forestry-related scenarios

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Further information

<https://www.go-surf.it/>

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